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The Needful Post COVID-19 Paradigm of Road Safety Ensures an Amicable Societal Continuance

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We the most rational human being does aspire for hazardless progressions of lives at all times. Therefore, they do try to ensure all the needful precautions in their most precious proceedings right from day one. On the other hand, common people do desire to elevate their collective education along with the absolute learning of both security and safety in all over the globe. Because this is such learning which may bring out the most even life based upon their communal aspirations in all the regards. People do have to move to a specific destination from another and that is the reason why they firmly do opt for transport without any second thought. The concepts of “Meticulous Transportation and Road Safety” are truly impactful not only to save our aspiring lives but to bring out the exclusive revolution in entrenching safety amongst the entire human fraternity. The actual fact is that almost every domestic family is having their personal vehicle and they do utilize their personal transport quite frequently. Present day statistics says that road accidents do take place and it is one of the very significant issues of present transport system indeed. As a result plenty of people are being hopeless because they have been losing their very precious lives uncontrollable road crashes and unwanted human behaviours respectively. Both leaders and administrators are not in a position to keep their moral commitments but they are trying to refine the “Traffic System” at every now and then. Thus the notion of “Road Safety Management” should immediately be implemented in all the “Business Schools” in their approved academic curriculum because this issue must be detected and consequentially prevented to protect human lives very confidently.

Keywords: Significance of road safety, societal impact, leader’s role, future consequence of road safety, administrative interference

Introduction

Pioneer leaders have entrenched the vivid foundation of “Industrial Safety” in both national and international stature. Most importantly they have been entirely concerned that “India” has been into the leading rank from the perspective of road accidents across 199 countries. They have tied up with “Law Commission of India” and according to their exclusive statistical report

50% of sufferers could have saved their lives if the rescue team would have really been active to take their most needful care on time. Social leaders, medical leaders, academic leaders shall have to be into the core and collective actions not only to detect the accidents which are of various kinds but they must establish a unique transport system where each vehicle shall have

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to abide by the traffic law and they must come under vehicle movement control at all times. The concept of “Traffic Control” shall have to be monitored by responsible administrators and they must be well trained by the “Government”. Leaders shall have to bring out “Traffic Management System” for our communal enrichment. This system should be really user friendly for all the appointed drivers, assistants and their vehicle owners at the same point of time.

Grinerud Katrine, Aarseth Wenche Kristin and Robertsen Rolf have told in one of the published Articles entitled: Leadership strategies, management decisions and safety culture in road transport organizations(2021) that, almost 688 people are injured due to heavy vehicle in Norway. There is HGV involved at every third road fatality.

The Paradigm of Root Management System:

Administrators and leaders must establish the system along with all the consequential possibilities. Most importantly this system should have the high-end occupational authority. It shall be very conducive to deploy all the trend leaders who will be following the certain rules:

1. Each safety leader must be evaluating the overall situation of a road right from day one. Because vehicle of all sorts do utilise the same throughout day and night as well. Leaders do have to coordinates with the appointed engineers about all the roads to be perceptually accomplished and refined. They have to allow all the heavy vehicles in a very befitting manner.
2. Engineers shall have to divide roads as per the availability of the vehicles and they shall have to restrict their speeds through speedometers. As a result all the vehicles will be under control and the profanity of accidents will be really less indeed.
3. Road constructors must be incorporating at the middle of any road which shall indicate the unethical driving at all times. On the other hand, traffic

administrators shall have to be very sound and active to focus upon this. The allotted penalty will be enforced on the occasion of any unusual movement of the cars on the road.

4. Vehicle verification spot will have to be introduced very shortly under this most important traffic law where at least heavy goods vehicles shall have to convey about their destinations along with the legitimate proofs of goods. It shall be easier for traffic guards to have the notice about the vehicle and about their roots as well.

5. Root navigator should be appointed out here. They will be responsible to navigate the fittest avenues to all the cars, buses, heavy vehicles just to maintain the amicable movements. In other words, they must be concerned about the scientific usage of different signals. Now the idea is people who are desirous to cross or walk upon the roads must hold the remote signal key and they shall have to appeal for the red to cross the road. Because common people should have this priority not only to utilize the hazardless road but they have to save their vital time and energy as well.

6. Root information kiosk should be immediately enforced and the concept of “By Lane” should be included out here. Every vehicle shall have the alert about the status of next avenue well in advance and on the other hand, common people shall have at least 10 foots road to walk. This decorum shall have to be well maintained and as a result the possibility of road accident will be reduced very shortly.

Wallius Eetu, Klock Ana Carolina Tome and Hamari Juho have told in their published article entitled: Playing it safe: A literature review and research agenda on motivational technologies in transportation safety (2022) that, motivation brings out the real affect in decision making, human reliability and technologies respectively.

The Primary Causes of Road Accidents

Road accidents are one of the most significant issues right now. The causes are as follows:

a. **Uncontrollable Speed:** Some of the vehicles seem really dangerous. They who drive the cars cannot control their speeds in any of the circumstances. As a result they are fallen in real trouble to stop or to turn anywhere and accidents do occur due to their most obstinate behaviours. We must keep the certain distance along with our immediate users otherwise drivers will not be able to control their speeds and the probability of risks will be higher accordingly. It should not be done at all. Because each traffic system is having some rules and each rule is having some specifications. Therefore, every car driver shall have to abide by the same once they are on the road. Otherwise few common people will lose their lives in a very hazardous manner and societal leaders will not be able maintain the desired societal legacy any more.

b. **Intoxication:** Alcoholic frame of mind is always very uncomfortable for a human being. It is a massive risk once they are driving the cars at all. Because it reduces the focus and enhances the stand of excitement within a short while. On the other hand, alcoholic drivers are entirely unmindful because alcohol destroys the coordination between mind and brain very shortly. Apart from that alcoholic brain deliberately provokes to take risks at every now and then. Therefore, accidents of various kinds do take place. It should be punishable crime. This allowance should immediately be stopped at all.

c. **Unethical practice:** Drivers do use mobile phones during driving and it is one of the major causes for them to be in massive road troubles. They do commit accidents quite frequently. Because mobile phone is one of the prime mediums for being addicted and it brings out the major attention of brain. That is why it is a real crime to use mobile phones during

driving and it has strenuous consequences in all the regards.

d. **Lack of experience:** It is one of the key factors to commit accidents on road. Plenty of drivers do drive the cars. But they do not have the requisite experience on the road. That is why they are not at all concerned about the signals and its impactful implementations. That is why they do face plenty of road hazards and accidents are of one kind. It is an absolute societal loss indeed.

e. **Ignorant Behaviour:** It causes the serious accidents at any time. Because it is noticed that drivers do establish their own desires while driving. They try to ignore traffic jams, minor and major congestions, signals, traffic guards and most notably common people. On the contrary they do not wear seat belts and helmets at all. As a result they do commit accidents which are against the society and the households respectively. Safety gears are very conducive to keep them very safe.

Morimoto Akinori, Wang Ailin and Kitano Naohiro have expressed their very important views in one of the published articles entitled: A conceptual framework for road traffic safety considering differences in traffic culture through international comparison (2022) that, many countries have given their needful efforts for road traffic safety while traffic safety goals are the most significant medium.

The Noteworthy Discussion

Government is already concerned about all the “Terrific Road Accidents” and that is why all the veteran leaders from our ministry should be thinking about one of the unique concepts. That is “Anti Road Accident Cell”. It should be enforced immediately in all over the globe.

This preventive cell must be having some prominent features, which are following:

1. Representation: A sound group of representatives must be appointed from each state of a country. They must be “Health Care Professionals” who will be taking care to all the injured passengers right from the accidental zone to hospitals/nursing homes. They must be having the connections both in state and national level where they may recommend their patients once it is absolutely required. On the other hand, representatives of each state must be having the noticeable coordination between them so that it shall be definitely possible to save more lives after any of the accidents indeed. We have seen that plenty of people do lose their precious lives just due to lacking of treatments on time. In this regard, all the representatives must be well educated and trained not only to ensure their collective liaison based upon the needs indeed. As a result all the effected people may have the amicable and solid treatments along with their collective moral, mental and psychological supports in the end and it is absolutely very conducive for both the family member of victims and those diligent state/national representatives to ensure this most pivotal recovery from the core of their collective occupational endurance.

2. Detective measures: “Anti Road Accident Cell” authority must be formed by the ministry. All the elite “Doctors, Social Workers, Road Safety Engineers, Health Care Professionals, Business magnets, Administrators” and so on must be involved. They will be seated together for the promotional meeting and they will be taking their own initiatives to detect all the accident prone zones based upon the quality of work, eligibility of manpower and traffic law respectively. They must be solely responsible not only to detect the zones but to supervise the entire process for both detecting and preventing the same along with all the promising representatives in the end. This is how this cell will be enforced and it shall be working for the mass. All the “Traffic Administrators and Controllers” will be recruited through this cell after field evaluations and interview. On the other

hand, they will be looking after about the amicable progression of cars and their legitimate movements.

3. Perceptual tie up: Anti road accident cell authority must be contacting with different academic institutes where “Health Care Management” is one of the major parts of their academic curriculum. It shall be very conducive for them to select some of the representatives who will be joining under this established preventive cell after going through the sequential process of selection for the accident victims. It will be their exclusive advantage not only to recruit those promising bunch of people but this cell will able to come at front to rescue those hopeless victims after accidents. All the academic principals shall have to come with their refining ideologies for this concept of “Road Safety” and they shall have to ensure their best academic curriculums based upon the same. The fact is they shall have to concentrate upon both health care management and nursing respectively. In other words, veteran “Principals” shall have to train these subjects based upon the present day scenario. Academic institutes do have the praiseworthy role to save all the accidents victims in both national and international arena. Most importantly this cell will be into the best occupational limelight within a very short while.

4. Awareness programme: Various awareness programmes and versatile workshops shall have to be exclusively conducted by the cell authority about road safety, causes of accidents, detective and preventive measures, their best protective organizational paradigms, different responsibilities, importance of road safety and its societal heritage, roles of post accident rescuers and so on. This authority shall have to invite to a number of experienced speakers who will be speaking about the needful resolutions in the end. This is how the exclusive paradigm of this cell will be truly flourished to the common mass and everybody shall have the mental strength about road safety without any second thought. Apart from the same ministry shall have to conduct different live talk

shows, conference, seminars just to enhance their public network in style.

5. **Impactful Leadership:** The concept of “Participative Leadership Approach” should be implemented here where both leaders and followers should be having the equal preference in the end. Leaders shall have to look after about their collective participations based upon the most introspective strategy. It says vehicles of all the sorts shall have the unique identification code and remote identifier will be enforced from this cell to detect their unusual practice on the road. Polls will be there at the very regular interval. So each “Remote Identifier” will have the certain limit. Therefore, all the cars shall have to carry that code once they are on the road. This is a sort of identification which will be very helpful not only to detect their unethical activities but to ensure the preventive measure at the same point of time. This is how this very cell will be more active through the utmost participations and involvements of our veteran leaders who will be driving the entire “Anti Road Accident Cell” along with their trained followers in a very conforming manner for safest tomorrow.

Aleksander Rydzewski and Pawel Czarnul have deciphered their epoch making views in one of the published articles entitled: Recent advances in traffic optimisation: Systematic literature review of modern models, methods and algorithms (2020) that, both increasing number of vehicles and imperfect traffic management are the actual cause of road congestion and health problems.

Corporate Social Responsibilities

It is absolutely needful for this most crucial initiative in the history. That is why leaders must bring out the following:

1. “Anti Road Accident Cell Authority” must be incorporating a registered NGO to have their moral, mental and psychological supports right from day one.

Moreover they might have some elite connections both in national and international standing who shall be providing the needful fund and they shall strengthen the existing community indeed.

2. Leaders must be refining the training potentials through implementing smart, experienced and quality trainers for meticulous transportation in the end. As a result roads will be safer in allowing common mass to utilise their risk free journey on the roads. Therefore, leaders must look after the process at all times.

3. Leaders must connect with a number of philanthropists to support road safety leaders through their patronage and their socio-economical supports based upon their needs. This is how that very cell will be enriched and overall refinement of “Road Safety” would simply be matter of time.

4. “Anti Road Accident Cell” will be creating some exclusive job opportunities at a very regular interval. All the desired people shall be able to apply and deserved candidates shall have the job under the sublime guidelines of their authority. They will be working according to “Road Safety Protection Act”. They shall have to detect all the accident prone zone and they shall have to establish the most salient rules and regulations. They shall have to save lives through their brilliant initiatives and health care professional will have to be truly responsible for their emergency medical treatments in the end.

5. 40% of the expenditure will be given by the cell authority at an emergency basis. So the action will be very fast and health care professionals will be admitting them in the hospitals and discharging them after the entire treatment is over. This is how these admirable activities will be regulated by the authority and core leaders of that community.

6. Leaders, doctors, health care professionals, nurses, road safety engineers, and willing learners

shall have to join this short but very significant academic course of “Road Safety Management”. The duration is only one month. They will be learning the entire legal paradigm in that course to implement into the practical fields and this is how road accidents will be almost out of picture over the coming years and this active “Anti Road Accident Cell” will definitely be rewarded. All the learners will definitely be certified by the authority.

Ahemed Mateen and Sugandhi Dr. Sunil have shared their most significant views in a published article entitled: Review Paper on RSA: A Descriptive Approach Towards Road Safety of Dhandhuka to Dholera (SH-20) In Gujrat State(2022) that, crores of people are injured and lakhs of people are died every year due to road accidents. The transport system has reduced the distance but the probability of life risk has already been increased.

Conclusion

Road safety is one of the most pivotal subjects in across the globe and researchers have granted this subject to do some extensive analysis to find out the most reasonable solution for bringing out the anticipated societal peace in the end. They firmly believe that people of all the statures do have their own existence and that is why all the available scientific introspections to entrench the hazardless evolution of “Road safety” over the coming days. It shall be truly overwhelming for the road users to enable the congratulatory metamorphosis of lives through their very long span of time. It is quite desirable to carry over the pertinent national legacy altogether.

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